

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN E-SERVICES AND PERCEIVED GOVERNMENT PERFORMANCE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CITIZENS AND PUBLIC EMPLOYEES IN ISLAMABAD

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Abstract

This research emphasized the impacts of e-governance on awareness, satisfaction and performance among citizens and employees, and to know differences between perception of citizens and employees on e-services. The revolutionary inclusion of ICT is promptly altering the social order and form of governance. E-governance and e-services system can be broken into four main categories: G2G (Government-to-Government), G2C (Government-to-Citizen), C2G (Citizen-to-Government), and C2C (Citizen-to-Citizen). This study has approximated the relationship between governments to citizens (G2C) and comprehends the impact on quality e-governance. The stratified sample technique adopted under the umbrella of convenience sampling for selection of the respondents. Further, the quantitative research method with deductive approach is applied to analyze the relationship. The statistical tool used to examine the reliability and validity of scales with factor analysis including cronbach alpha, anova, correlation, regression through SPSS version 25. As e-governance system aims to facilitate the citizens, there is important interaction between federal government employees and citizens. It is found that awareness, satisfaction and performance from the perspective of citizens are favorable but not in case of employees' performance due to their low experience. This study is limited to Islamabad with unavailability of providing e-services where the focus for better efficiency and delivery services about data protection law, and single portal for all e-services. It is recommended that improve the skilled & technological education system, adoption of new technology and increasing awareness can enhance e-governance efficiency and service delivery.

INTRODUCTION

The rise of e-governance globally has transformed the way governments interact with citizens and businesses, offering digital solutions to improve service delivery, transparency, and efficiency (Qina, 2015). In developed nations, e-governance has

successfully streamlined administrative processes, enhanced citizen engagement, and promoted economic growth (Atiq et al., 2023). Similarly, developing countries are increasingly adopting digital governance tools to bridge gaps in public service

delivery and governance inefficiencies (El Madawi, 2020).

E-services have become pivotal in modern governance, offering platforms for secure, transparent, and efficient government-to-citizen (G2C), government-to-business (G2B), and government-to-government (G2G) interactions (Ronchi, 2019). The adoption of e-services improves accessibility, reduces bureaucratic hurdles, and enhances responsiveness in public administration (Khadka, 2024). The rapid expansion of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has provided a strong foundation for governments worldwide to transition from manual processes to automated digital systems (Daniels-Heath, 2023).

In Pakistan, e-governance has gained significant attention as a mechanism to improve service delivery, transparency, and public administration (CSPPA, 2022). Islamabad, the capital city, has been at the forefront of implementing digital governance initiatives, with efforts directed at modernizing public service platforms, increasing digital literacy, and enhancing government-citizen interaction. However, despite numerous initiatives, challenges such as digital infrastructure constraints, policy gaps, and limited public awareness continue to hinder the full realisation of e-governance potential (Chilembo, 2021). The evolution of e-governance in Pakistan can be traced back to the early 2000s when the Ministry of Information Technology introduced the e-Government Directorate (Sharma et al., 2022). Since then, various projects have been launched to digitalize public services, such as online tax filing, digital land records, and automated citizen grievance redressal mechanisms (Sharma et al., 2022). However, the implementation of these projects has faced obstacles due to political instability, inadequate technological infrastructure, and resistance to change within government institutions (Sovacool et al., 2024). As a developing country, Pakistan faces unique challenges in adopting e-governance, including disparities in digital access between urban and rural areas, low levels of ICT literacy, and concerns over data security (Rashid & Rashid, 2023). Nonetheless, the potential benefits of e-governance remain significant. A well-integrated digital governance framework can enhance governmental efficiency, foster citizen participation, and create an

environment conducive to socio-economic development (Hao et al., 2022). Islamabad, being the administrative and political hub of Pakistan, has been a focal point for e-governance initiatives (CSPPA, 2022). The city's governance framework has witnessed efforts to digitise public records, introduce smart city concepts, and integrate ICT-based solutions in various government departments (Fatima, 2022). Key initiatives include online portals for utility bill payments, digital complaint management systems, and electronic documentation for government services (Qina, 2015).

Despite these advancements, Islamabad's e-governance landscape still encounters issues related to interoperability between government systems, limited public adoption of digital platforms, and gaps in cybersecurity measures (Malik, 2023). Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive strategy that involves policy reform, investment in ICT infrastructure, and capacity-building programs to ensure the sustainable growth of e-governance in Pakistan (Khan et al., 2024). This study examines the development of e-governance in Pakistan with a specific focus on Islamabad. It aims to assess the efficiency of e-services, identify key challenges, and propose solutions to enhance the effectiveness of digital governance in the country. By integrating socio-economic perspectives, this research seeks to contribute to the discourse on how Pakistan can leverage e-governance for improved public service delivery and governance reform (Udoh, 2024).

1.2. Problem Statement

The purpose of this study is to provide a theoretical framework that defines the perspectives of citizens and government employees in the implementation of e-governance in Islamabad's public service sector. While extensive research exists on the adoption of e-government in developed countries, there is limited research on Pakistan's experience. Each study on e-governance has examined different factors in various contexts, leading to fragmented findings.

A major issue facing state-building efforts today is the absence of clear and standardised models that define the steps for implementing e-governance programmes. In Pakistan, despite the widespread introduction of e-government policies, their impact on improving the quality of governance remains

uncertain. One fundamental challenge is the lack of a financially viable plan that effectively meets real demands. Implementing large-scale changes in public service delivery requires a structured approach to navigating an unfamiliar and evolving digital environment. The absence of a consensus on the challenges of e-governance adoption has resulted in conflicting views in existing literature.

This study aims to identify the most suitable strategies for planning and deploying e-services to enhance the effectiveness of Islamabad's e-governance system. It is divided into two key areas: measuring citizens' and government employees' perceptions of e-governance. Additionally, it seeks to evaluate the impact of digital platforms on public administration by examining how e-services influence the efficiency of government employees.

By identifying differences between citizen and employee perspectives on e-governance, this study will provide government officials with insights into the challenges and barriers associated with implementing e-services. Furthermore, it will highlight public expectations regarding digital governance. By monitoring the impact of e-services on regulatory processes, this research will contribute to strategies for improving the quality and effectiveness of e-governance in Islamabad. This study aims to investigate the impact of e-governance on the awareness, satisfaction, and performance of e-services among both citizens and government employees. It seeks to assess how perceptions of e-services differ between these two groups, highlighting potential gaps in expectations and experiences. Additionally, the study will explore the broader implications of e-services on the effectiveness of e-governance, examining whether digital initiatives enhance transparency, efficiency, and overall governmental performance.

To achieve these objectives, the research will address key questions: What is the impact of e-governance on the awareness, satisfaction, and performance of e-services among citizens and employees? How do perceptions of e-services vary between citizens and government employees? What role do e-services play in shaping the success of e-governance initiatives? By answering these questions, the study will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of digital

governance and its influence on public service delivery in Islamabad.

2. Literature Review

2.1 E-Government Services

Extensive review of literature on concepts and concepts related to e-government services is provided (Gupta et al., 2016). The purpose of reviewing research papers and articles is to publish and test the work done in this field. Electronic government is a convenient and powerful tool that allows different countries to develop and control their systems with excellent reliability, accuracy, and transparency (Ndou, 2004). With a strong response from the community, the system has expanded the pipeline to provide better services in different areas. In this section, researchers collect information in journals, journals, journals, and website files. This section provides a summary of the literature on each topic. The researcher has identified research papers published in renowned journals and conference proceedings along with articles published in newspapers on various topics.

The development of information and communication technologies has a great potential for many public companies to provide the best service without interruption (Gungor et al., 2011). The advent of ICT has brought about a huge change in the business world. Many countries use the Internet on a daily basis in other programs. All over the world, our World Wide Web has made great strides in providing valuable services to citizens with many benefits of ICT. It plays a major role in changing their policies in government, commerce, political affairs, economics, and public relations. It allows the public to converse more efficiently, interact more efficiently, use equipment more efficiently, and provide useful services. The main advantages of using ICT are: It increases the competence and speed of services to the public, reduces costs, time, manpower, and exhaustion. ICT supports government activities through its clear delivery methodology and framework that can be implemented in accordance with its rules and regulations (Postholm, 2007).

2.2 Role of ICT in Public Services

E-government can be described as a science that interacts well with information and communication

technologies. Many authors are different. All the details you have been given are given, but they are not called because of something new and innovative. E-government can accelerate and promote economic growth. Visiting government offices is a big problem. It presents many novels, long queues, bureaucracy, hard lives, and many tragedies (Hood, 2010). With the increasing demands of citizens, in addition to changes in international laws and regulations, government agencies have had to use ICT effectively for their services. The primary goal of e-government is to create a human government that is highly dependent on its territory, including political, cultural, economic, social, and technological systems. (Hussain et al., 2024)

2.3 Fundamentals and Challenges of E-Government

Mohammed Alshehri and Steve Drew have published their article in 2010 on "E-Government Fundamentals" in which they described that effective e-government is becoming an important aim for many governments around the world (Nguyen-Duc et al., 2021). In this context, this article aims to review and restructure the previous work on e-government, such as the definition of e-government, types, types, benefits, and constraints of e-government. It provides the necessary background knowledge for the research topic, as well as highlights the key concepts of e-government. E-government has the potential to significantly improve the way governments work with each other and serve their customers. E-government is much more than a tool for improving the cost-quality ratio in public services (Khayat, 2010). However, the implementation of e-government faces many serious problems, some of which are non-specific in nature and have many implications and require special planning. The results of this article indicate that it is important to carry out an in-depth study of the challenges posed in the implementation of e-government and to find solutions to understand these barriers. Pakistan is a developing country and the new government is reading about electricity in the media, but the people of Pakistan do not need electricity because there are so many processes (Jan et al., 2023). The absence of a unified and adaptable framework for implementing e-governance initiatives in Pakistan reflects broader challenges in public sector innovation. As Iftikhar et al. (2022) argue,

redefining the parameters of social innovation through comprehensive conceptual models is essential to support systemic transformations in governance and service delivery.

Through research and study of models, Pakistan has become popular among e-government and confidence in foreign services has increased. Here is a list of email services, including college, taxes, fees, mobility, employment, race, health, and care benefits. This study has made it easy for many readers to find information on your needs. The government of Pakistan now needs more research in this area to implement a policy of physical action against the undeveloped areas.

2.4 Functions and Models of E-Government

E-Government provides a variety of functions for public servants, citizens, business owners, and officials through wireless means (Ndou, 2004). E-governance guarantees the provision of online services to connect an individual to another user and a branch of government to another branch. This article discusses different types or possible models of e-government, in government to government (G2G), government to business (G2B), government to citizens (G2C), and governments and their employees (G2E). Muhammad Ali and Norin Mujahid, in their 2015 article, "Pakistan Case Study Electronic Government Re-Administration," described the study as a useful tool for improving e-government. For the 20th consecutive year, e-government is taking its first steps (Alcaide-Muñoz et al., 2017). In one way or another, all countries in the world promote e-government as a means of reducing costs, saving time, improving social services, and improving the quality and efficiency of services. The state social services in Pakistan are promoting electronic systems as a new concept. However, as a developed country, it faces significant challenges in adopting e-government and public services. The aim of this study was to examine how e-government works in public administration to identify opportunities and challenges for governments and public authorities (Ebrahim & Irani, 2005). E-government is approaching its embryonic stage and will soon enter the stage of development in Pakistan (Ali & Mujahid, 2015). If the government takes appropriate and revolutionary steps to implement e-

government, there is no doubt that we can become a model for developing and neighboring countries. However, there are many challenges and obstacles in adopting e-government, such as lack of infrastructure, conservative thinking about bureaucracy, language barriers, and low literacy, which the government has to consider carefully. Pakistan also has to reorganize its national documents and information infrastructure and initiate a change in e-government (Chandio et al., 2018). This can be achieved through sectoral development processes and the creation of integrated network-based networks.

2.5. Theoretical and Analytical Framework

Awareness refers to an individual's recognition and understanding of e-services, influencing their willingness to engage with digital platforms (Yaseen, 2017). Satisfaction pertains to users' contentment with e-services, shaped by factors such as efficiency, accessibility, and data security (Sharma & Lijuan, 2015). Performance is the extent to which e-services enhance operational effectiveness and user experience, ensuring transparency, accountability, and responsiveness (Saif Murshed Almeqbaali, 2022). E-services, a core component of e-governance, facilitate digital transactions and service delivery between government entities and citizens, improving efficiency and reducing corruption (Alam, 2015). The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework, developed by (Venkatesh et al., 2016) identifies key determinants influencing the adoption of e-services. Performance expectancy measures users' belief that e-services will enhance job performance, while effort expectancy

evaluates the perceived ease of use of digital platforms (Razak et al., 2017). Social influence assesses the impact of societal norms on e-service adoption, and facilitating conditions determine the adequacy of technical and organisational support for system usage (Tsourela & Roumeliotis, 2015). These variables collectively shape the adoption and effectiveness of e-services in governance structures.

The analytical framework illustrates the interaction between e-services and key performance indicators, examining their influence on users (citizens) and providers (employees). The quality of e-services is assessed through awareness, satisfaction, and performance metrics, which determine the effectiveness of digital governance initiatives (Salam, 2013). The model emphasises the importance of accessibility, local language support, and public acceptance in user engagement (Ndou, 2004). For providers, efficiency, rule of law, and transparency shape the successful implementation of e-services (Ciborra, 2005). E-services serve as the independent variable, directly impacting performance, which is the dependent variable (Alam et al., 2021). Awareness and satisfaction act as mediating variables, influencing the extent to which e-services achieve their intended objectives (Lepcha, 2020). Awareness is measured through factors such as ease of use, information dissemination, and support structures (Iyer, 2020). Satisfaction is evaluated based on accessibility, service efficiency, and data security (Hai et al., 2024). Performance is assessed using parameters such as transparency, accountability, and responsiveness in service delivery (Holgersson & Karlsson, 2014).

This framework establishes a structured approach to examining the adoption and effectiveness of e-services in public governance, ensuring that digital platforms enhance efficiency, accessibility, and user satisfaction across government sectors.

3-Research Methodology

The study examines the implications of e-governance services for effective communication and usage, focusing on e-service users and providers in Islamabad. The objective is to identify and evaluate factors influencing the adoption of e-governance systems in the capital city of Pakistan. The research follows an analytical framework based on prior literature and incorporates a structured methodology that includes the theoretical framework, data collection methods, and econometric techniques.

The study adopts a quantitative research design, as statistical analysis is required to evaluate awareness, satisfaction, and performance levels of e-governance services. This approach aligns with recent empirical studies that have examined determinants of e-governance adoption using similar constructs and methodologies (Hayat et al. 2025). Among the major research approaches inductive, deductive, and abductive—the deductive approach is selected since it enables reasoning from general to specific. This aligns with the nature of the study, which involves hypothesis testing using numerical data. The research

also follows the post-positivist paradigm, which is best suited for quantitative studies, ensuring an objective assessment of the impact of e-governance services. The research is conducted in Islamabad, the federal capital of Pakistan. The city is an urbanized administrative hub where various e-governance initiatives have been implemented. Islamabad covers an area of 906 square kilometers, with both urban and rural zones, and serves as the focal point for the study due to the government's early adoption of e-governance services in the region.

The study targets two primary groups: citizens from five zones of Islamabad and employees from relevant federal public service institutions responsible for implementing and managing e-governance services. Citizens are selected from various administrative zones of Islamabad, ensuring representation from different socio-economic backgrounds. Employees are chosen from key government departments providing e-services, including NADRA, Excise and Taxation Department, PMDU, Capital Territory Police, and CDA/MCI. A stratified random sampling technique is used under a convenience framework. Given the heterogeneity of the population, stratification ensures that respondents from different zones and professional backgrounds are adequately represented. The selection process is further refined using simple random sampling,

ensuring a fair and unbiased representation of both citizens and government employees. Data is collected through structured questionnaires, designed based on prior literature on e-governance adoption. Two separate questionnaires are used—one for citizens and one for government employees—to assess awareness, satisfaction, and performance levels. The survey uses a five-point Likert scale to measure perceptions regarding e-governance services. The questionnaire consists of multiple sections, including demographic information, e-service usage, and overall assessment of e-governance efficiency. The study employs a combination of reliability testing, correlation and regression analysis, ANOVA, and factor analysis to evaluate the collected data. Cronbach’s Alpha is used to test the reliability of the measurement scales, ensuring consistency in responses. Correlation and regression analyses help determine the relationships between independent variables (awareness, satisfaction, performance) and the dependent variable (quality of e-governance). ANOVA is applied to compare differences in perceptions across various demographic groups. Factor analysis identifies patterns and simplifies variable relationships for better interpretation.

4. Results and Analysis

The demographic profile of respondents includes both citizens and government employees from Islamabad. The study surveyed 260 citizens and 220 government employees. Among the citizens, the majority (36.2%) were within the 35-45 age group, followed by 33.5% in the 25-35 age range. The level of education among respondents showed that 40.8% had a bachelor's degree, 29.2% had a master’s degree, while 22.7% had completed intermediate education. The employment distribution indicated that 23.8% of the respondents were private employees, 5.4% were government employees, 9.6% were students, and 18.8% were unemployed. Regarding gender distribution, 53.5% of respondents were male, and 46.5% were female (Alam, 2015).

For government employees, 28.9% were aged between 35-45, and 22.9% were between 25-35 years old. The highest level of education among employees was a master’s degree (27.1%), followed by a bachelor’s degree (24.3%) and an M.Phil (11.4%). Gender distribution showed that 33.4% of respondents were male and 29.4% were female. The educational background suggests that most employees involved in e-governance have at least a bachelor’s degree, indicating a highly literate workforce (Tavakoli et al., 2008).

S.NO.	Age Groups	
1.	25 to 35	33.5 %
2.	35 to 45	36.2 %
3.	45 to above all	30.4 %
Education Complete		
1.	Intermediate	22.7 %
2.	Bachelors	40.8 %
3.	Masters	29.2%
4.	M.Phill	7.3 %
Occupational Status		
1.	Govt. Employee	5.4 %
2.	Private employee	23.8 %
3.	Self Employed	5.4 %
4.	Student	9.6 %
5.	Unemployed	18.8 %
6.	House Wife	23.5 %

Gender status		
1.	Male	53.5 %
2.	Female	46.5 %

The study examined awareness, satisfaction, and performance among citizens and employees regarding e-governance services. The age-wise response ratio for e-services usage revealed that the 25-35 age group had the highest awareness and usage rates (24.2%), followed by the 35-45 group (23.2%). In contrast, individuals above 45 years showed a lower engagement with e-governance, primarily due to a lack of digital literacy and preference for manual systems (Chen et al., 1986).

Regarding satisfaction with e-services, both male and female respondents demonstrated a high level of approval, with 28.9% of males and 33.3% of females expressing satisfaction. However, the age-wise satisfaction analysis indicated that 25.9% of respondents were not satisfied with the current e-governance services, highlighting areas for improvement (Kumbhar, 2012).

Government employees were also assessed based on their provision and experience with e-governance services. Employees aged 35-45 were the primary facilitators of digital services, with 45.9% actively engaged in delivering utility bill payment services online. However, employees above 45 years showed less participation due to technological constraints (Alam, 2015).

4.1 Regression Results: Impact of E-Services on Performance

Regression analysis was conducted to examine the impact of e-services on performance. The model for citizens indicated that awareness, satisfaction, and performance were positively associated with quality e-governance, explaining 29.2%, 28.4%, and 21.7% of the variance, respectively. The coefficient for awareness ($\beta = 0.217, p < 0.05$) showed that increased awareness significantly improved perceptions of e-governance quality. Similarly, satisfaction ($\beta = 0.209, p < 0.05$) was found to be a crucial determinant of e-governance adoption. Performance ($\beta = 0.140, p < 0.05$) also had a significant impact, suggesting that when government employees are well-trained and skilled, public trust in e-governance improves (Nunally et al., 1994).

For employees, regression results revealed that awareness ($\beta = 0.019, p < 0.05$) and satisfaction ($\beta = 0.048, p < 0.05$) positively contributed to quality e-governance, whereas performance ($\beta = -0.125, p < 0.05$) had a negative impact. The negative performance coefficient suggests that untrained employees hinder the effectiveness of e-governance implementation. This finding underscores the need for training programs to improve employee competencies in delivering e-governance services (Tavakoli et al., 2008).

Source	SS	df	MS		F (3, 260)	=	2563.74
Model	5152.0757	3	1717.359		Prob> F	=	0.0000
Residual	12378.4482	18479	0.669866		R-squared	=	0.2939
Total	17530.5239	18482	0.948519		Adj R-squared	=	0.2938
					Root MSE	=	0.81845
Quality E-governance	coef.	std. Err.	T	P > t	[95% Conf.	Interval	
Awareness	0.2178602	0.013134	16.59	0.0000	0.192116	0.243604	
Satisfaction	0.2099309	0.01049	20.01	0.0000	0.189369	0.230449	
Performance	0.140396	0.010848	12.94	0.0000	0.119133	0.161659	
(Constant)	0.0546658	0.006033	9.06	0.0000	0.042841	0.066491	

4.2 Comparative Perception Analysis: Citizens vs. Government Employees

The study compared citizen and employee perceptions of e-governance services. The majority of citizens (23.8%) agreed that e-governance services improved access to public services, whereas 22.7% strongly disagreed, preferring manual methods. The perception of e-services as user-friendly was mixed, with only 15.4% agreeing that they were easy to use, while 21.9% found them difficult to navigate (Chen et al., 1986).

Among government employees, 53.6% believed that e-governance improved efficiency, while 46.4% disagreed. A further 50.9% of employees stated that e-governance services enhanced citizen satisfaction, whereas 49.1% were skeptical about its impact. The mixed perceptions suggest that while e-governance has potential, issues such as digital literacy, system usability, and technical support must be addressed to improve acceptance (Tavakoli et al., 2008).

Several patterns emerged from the analysis. First, younger citizens (25-35 years) were more likely to use e-governance services, while older individuals (above 45) preferred traditional methods. Second, government employees in the 35-45 age bracket were the most active in implementing e-governance initiatives. Third, e-police services, online tax payments, and utility bill payments were the most frequently used e-services, whereas administrative services like domicile issuance had lower adoption rates (Kumbhar, 2012).

A notable anomaly was the discrepancy in employee perceptions of performance. While awareness and satisfaction were positively correlated with e-governance efficiency, employee performance had a negative impact. This suggests that while employees acknowledge the benefits of e-governance, inadequate training and resistance to technological change hinder its full implementation (Alam, 2015).

Overall, the results highlight the need for targeted policy interventions to enhance e-governance adoption. Awareness campaigns, usability improvements, and employee training programs are essential to bridge the gap between citizen expectations and government service delivery. The study concludes that while e-governance has the potential to revolutionize public service delivery, its success depends on strategic improvements in

awareness, satisfaction, and workforce performance (Chen et al., 1986).

5. Discussion

The findings of this study align with the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model, confirming that awareness, satisfaction, and performance play a crucial role in the adoption of e-governance services. The study demonstrates that e-services enhance transparency, efficiency, and accountability, supporting previous research (Ahmad, 2014; Iyer, 2010). The research also highlights the challenges faced in e-governance implementation, including infrastructure limitations, lack of digital skills, resistance to change among employees and citizens, and concerns over trust and data security.

The study indicates that younger citizens are more aware and satisfied with e-services than older individuals. This gap suggests that while digital transformation has improved service delivery, there is a need for targeted initiatives to enhance digital literacy among older age groups. The findings also reveal that federal employees acknowledge the benefits of e-governance in reducing workload and improving service delivery, aligning with the results of Jean Damascene Twizeyimanaa (2019). However, resistance to change and lack of comprehensive training remain barriers to the full adoption of digital services in government institutions. Overcoming institutional resistance and digital illiteracy among public sector employees requires context-specific strategies that address both structural and behavioral barriers. Iqbal et al. (2024) emphasize the role of innovative strategies in enhancing technology adoption, especially in resource-constrained environments, which can be highly relevant for improving e-governance uptake in developing contexts like Pakistan.

A significant gap exists between e-governance policies and their practical implementation. Although Pakistan has introduced several e-services platforms, such as the City Islamabad App, many citizens and employees still struggle with accessibility and user-friendliness. The findings show that while citizens appreciate the convenience of online services, they express concerns over security and technical difficulties, which are consistent with previous studies (Salam, 2013; Alam, 2015).

The study further emphasizes that while the government has initiated various e-services, the integration of these services across different departments remains a challenge. Employees report that e-governance has reduced paperwork and improved transparency, yet they still rely on manual processes due to incomplete digital infrastructure. These findings suggest that a hybrid approach, where traditional and digital services work in parallel, may be necessary until full integration is achieved.

This study examines the awareness, satisfaction, and performance of citizens and employees in relation to e-governance services in Islamabad. The results confirm that e-governance enhances service delivery, reduces bureaucracy, and increases transparency, yet its success is dependent on public awareness and technological infrastructure (Hussain et al., 2024). The research highlights that younger citizens are more engaged with e-services, while older populations and some government employees exhibit resistance to change due to lack of digital literacy.

The findings have important policy implications, particularly in terms of improving data security, infrastructure investment, and capacity-building initiatives. The government should focus on expanding ICT training programs for employees and citizens, ensuring that digital services are user-friendly and accessible to all age groups. Additionally, enhancing public trust in e-governance by strengthening cybersecurity measures and ensuring data privacy will be crucial for widespread adoption.

In terms of contribution to e-governance literature in developing countries, this study provides empirical evidence on the impact of e-governance in Pakistan, identifying both its potential and the barriers to its success. It highlights the importance of aligning digital transformation initiatives with the needs of both service providers and users to ensure efficient implementation.

Despite its contributions, this study has limitations, including its geographical focus on Islamabad, which may not reflect the digital governance experience of rural areas. Future research should expand the scope to include other cities and regions to gain a comprehensive understanding of e-governance adoption in Pakistan. Additionally, while this study used quantitative analysis, future research could incorporate qualitative methods, such as interviews

and case studies, to explore the deeper socio-cultural aspects of digital governance adoption (Akram et al., 2024).

For policy interventions, the study recommends that the government standardize digital platforms, improve inter-departmental coordination, and introduce incentives for employees to adopt digital workflows. By addressing these challenges, Pakistan can create a sustainable and efficient e-governance ecosystem, ultimately leading to better public service delivery and greater citizen engagement.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of e-governance on citizens' and government employees' awareness, satisfaction, and performance within Islamabad's public service sector. Findings reveal that while citizens generally perceive e-governance positively reporting increased accessibility, satisfaction, and trust in digital services—government employees exhibited mixed responses, largely due to insufficient training and technological adaptation. The analysis highlights that awareness and satisfaction significantly contribute to the effectiveness of e-governance, whereas employee performance can hinder progress without adequate digital literacy. Moreover, younger populations are more engaged with e-services, pointing to generational divides in digital adoption. Despite the promising initiatives like online tax filing and digital complaint systems, challenges such as interoperability, limited digital infrastructure, and security concerns persist. To maximize the potential of e-governance, the study recommends enhanced ICT training, user-friendly service design, integrated platforms, and robust cybersecurity frameworks. This research contributes to the discourse on digital transformation in developing countries and underscores the need for inclusive, citizen-centric approaches to e-governance implementation. Future studies should expand geographically and incorporate qualitative insights to deepen understanding of socio-cultural factors influencing digital governance in Pakistan.

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